

SOCIO-PEDAGOGICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF IMPROVING THE SOCIAL ACTIVITY OF STUDENTS IN PEDAGOGICAL HIGHER EDUCATION ON THE BASIS OF HISTORICAL KNOWLEDGE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6801586>

Annotation: This article focuses on the emergence of historical knowledge, the role of historical knowledge in enhancing students' social activism competencies.

Keywords and concepts: history, historical knowledge, competence, social activism, New Uzbekistan, education

At the time when the world community is rapidly developing, all fields are enriched with news related to scientific relations. In particular, every day new knowledge and technologies enter the field of education, which defines an important direction for mankind to find its place in the life of society. This process is considered to be an important factor for education and training to keep pace with the times in the scientific environment, and demands the introduction of new methods, assigning important tasks to pedagogues. If the education system is not renewed and improved, the quality of education will continue to decline. At this point, strong attention is being paid to education in our country, and important tasks are being set to further improve the quality of education.

It is appropriate to properly organize the implementation of decrees and decisions in the field of education adopted by the President and the government in order to train young people, who are the future of our country, to receive quality education and become qualified and mature intellectual potential. PF-5847 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 8, 2019 "On approval of the concept of development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" [1], "On approval of the national program for the development of public education in 2022-2026" dated May 11, 2022 [2]] decrees, dated April 20, 2017 No. PQ-2909 "On measures to further develop the higher education system" [3], dated June 5, 2018 No. PQ-3775 "Increasing the quality of education in higher education institutions and their comprehensive implementation in the country "On additional measures to ensure active participation in reforms" [4] indicates that large-scale reforms are being implemented in the field of education. In the "Concept of the development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" it was said, "based on international experience, the introduction of advanced standards of

higher education, including the step-by-step transition from education focused on acquiring theoretical knowledge to an educational system focused on the formation of practical skills" it is emphasized that In addition, the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 in the direction of conducting a fair social policy, developing human capital, "Bringing the quality of education in the preschool education system to a new level, improving the quality of education in secondary schools, bringing the knowledge and skills of pedagogues to the international level, priority goals such as "to reach the coverage level of higher education to 50% and to improve the quality of education" are set.

Also, in the decree "On the approval of the national program for the development of public education in 2022-2026" signed by the President Sh.M.Mirziyoev, the practice of training pedagogues based on competence-based and professional skills training in national centers for training pedagogues in new methodologies, i.e. Pedagogical centers a number of tasks were assigned.

An important factor is the practical implementation of such advanced steps in the path of development of New Uzbekistan.

The strategy of fundamental changes implemented in our country is based not only on national values and traditions, but also on the use of advanced world experience. It is appropriate to bring the development of the national education system of Uzbekistan to a new stage and to implement it with a scientific and creative approach, taking into account the achievements of foreign countries. In this regard, the role of historical knowledge gained as a result of mastering the lessons of the history of Uzbekistan is incomparable in the development of pedagogical higher education students to become qualified pedagogues with mature intellectual potential. The science of history is a holistic study of the events and processes that have occurred in the life of society throughout the entire past of humanity.[5] Historical knowledge - knowledge about the development of human society in historical time. The conditions for the emergence of such knowledge are explained by the formation of the idea of \u200b\u200bphased time in the human mind and the appearance of writing. Historical knowledge was created in different countries at different times. According to some information that has reached us, the first of the historical works dates back to the millennium BC. It is an ancient Egyptian chronicle of the 25th century. Historical knowledge in Europe BC. It appeared in VI-V centuries. In Russia, it is said that historical knowledge appeared in the form of historical chronicles in the X-XI centuries. In our country, we can know from the results of research that historical knowledge was created much earlier than in Egypt or

European countries. Therefore, the history of our country is richer and more ancient than that of other countries. Historical knowledge is considered a broad concept and is one of the important factors for human development and gaining a place in society. A number of sources and materials can be used to increase social activity through historical knowledge, especially for students who have set a specific goal and are trying to find their place in society. In particular, along with traditions, chronicles and historical stories, journalistic essays, scientific articles, reviews, monographs, historical poems, novels, films and television films, historical paintings and sculptures are forms of historical knowledge. It is also important to use history textbooks and manuals based on current historical research and archaeological excavations.

The impact of historical knowledge gained from the study of history can be both positive and negative. In the process of studying history, there are exemplary people who we can learn from, and on the contrary, there have been events that darken our hearts due to the mistakes and shortcomings of some historical person. During the study of these, human thinking improves and it is natural to have a negative or positive opinion about the studied historical event or the behavior of a historical person. If he can approach the process correctly and evaluate it objectively, the learned history will definitely be a programmatic practice and experience in his future life. The more knowledge a person has, the more his worldview and views on society expand.

Students of pedagogical higher education, as future pedagogues, teach the essence of the democratic reforms implemented in our country, the establishment of a national legal democratic state, the construction of a free civil society, the further improvement of the socially oriented market economy, the glorification of human dignity and worth, and teach young people the national outlook, political and educates scientific culture, helps him to define his place in society properly and correctly. The most important thing is to deeply understand the nature of all the reforms being implemented and understand that they are related to change and renewal.

The greatness and power of our nation is determined by its rich spiritual and historical heritage. Therefore, the historical and spiritual foundation of our nation is ancient and strong, and every future pedagogue striving for a bright future should study this spiritual heritage and try to become a generation worthy of our great ancestors as a socially active person with historical knowledge. After all, the first president of the Republic of Uzbekistan, I.A. Karimov, said that "a nation that does not know its history and forgets its past

has no future"[6]. Every future pedagogue can study our rich ancient history in depth and come to the conclusion that he should always remember the rich scientific and spiritual discoveries, victories and courage of our great ancestors who gave hope and confidence to our people even in the most fragile and dangerous times, and behave as a generation worthy of them. I think it is necessary. It is no exaggeration to say that in order to convey our great heritage to students, in addition to history lessons, trips to historical places and monuments, organizing tours to museums will help us enrich their historical knowledge even more.

In conclusion, we can say that as a result of the accumulation of historical knowledge, students' interest in the history and rich spiritual heritage of our national statehood will increase, and students will become socially active qualified personnel. Nowadays, it is the duty of every pedagogue to show social activity in the life of society. A student armed with historical knowledge, that is, a future pedagogue, becomes a person who helps students to work effectively in the future for the development of the Motherland, as well as improving their education and knowledge potential.

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